

A profile of Antecedents in selecting a Higher Education Institution

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ABSTRACT

Indian higher education system is one of the largest in terms of enrolments; more than 800 universities and 25000 plus higher education institutions make the education industry as competitive and vibrant one. Engineering education, in particular, recognized as a niche section with more than 1.5 million students. In Tamil Nadu, more than 580 colleges engaging in the engineering education. However, in the recent times, the enrolment numbers are staggering and every year more number of seats left unfilled. One of the reason often quoted for the shutting down is quality of faculty and delivery of required inputs. In this background, the current research work aims to address the differences in factors considered for choosing an education institution and gender differences in evaluating the importance attached to the select list of antecedents. The results confirmed that there is a gender difference and male respondents have given significantly lower importance for all the attributes. Safe and Friendly Environment, Learning Environment and Job Prospects, Reputation, Placement and Soft & Hard Infrastructure received highest importance while selecting a higher education institution.

1. Introduction

In India, the higher education is provided under three categories of institutions; (i) Universities and University level institutions [where they empower to award degree under an act of Parliament or State legislature], (ii) Colleges / Institutions [Not authorized to award degree, but affiliate with universities] and (iii) Stand-alone Institutions [not affiliated with any universities, however, empower to award of Diploma Programmes]. In the post-independent era, there is a steady growth in the higher education enrolments, new institutions, and new branches of education; today there are millions of stakeholders, 1000s of colleges, 800 + universities. However, these institutions failed to secure niche position in the global market place. Many institutions have sub-standard infrastructure, poor quality of teachers and with little degree of standardization. In particular, engineering education institutions suffer a lot in the recent years, where many institutions are on the verge of closing their operations. In Tamil Nadu, there were too many seats vacant in the engineering colleges for the last several years. Thus, a research which can provide insights on student's selection process and importance attached to various attributes, will be immense helpful to understand the present day situation. This research work aims in creating a profile of the student's evaluation of various factors while choosing an engineering college will render more insights and information for the administrators to manage them properly. These insights will help them to closely monitor as well as use the attributes in the admission process to highlight the salient features of the institution.

2. Review of Earlier Studies and Hypothesis

Decades ago, many research studies conducted to bring out the role of Word-of-Mouth Communication [WOM] in higher education contexts; a study by Herr et al proved that WOM has significant role to develop favorable as well as stronger brand

attitude, even though the decision maker is left with huge amount of diagnostic information. Ennew et al (2000) study conducted in Northern India inferred that active management of WOM communication through customer referral campaigns helps increase the spread of WOM.

A research on higher education institution brand equity suggests that brand image, brand identity and brand soul to be integrated together and work in the same direction to create better brand equity (Robert and Maktoba, 2014). Another study findings from Malaysian context reported that people with strong attachment with their higher education institution willing to spend more resources and money to maintain their status quo with the institution (Ramli et al 2015).

Rojas-Mendez et al (2009) work on determinants student loyalty in higher education perceived service quality and satisfaction are having significant predicting power of loyalty. Bergamo et al (2012) also confirmed that perceived service quality and students satisfaction are the two most important predictors of loyalty.

Pre-selection factors of a higher education institution

Students' selection of an institution is not a just overnight decision; it is a careful analysis of information and a crafted decision based on many parameters. In addition, very rarely, admissions are taking place based on single dimensional considerations. Monica et al (2014) study has identified soft and hard infrastructure, Alumni and student recommendation, media influence, placement opportunities and fees and location as important pre-selection variables by the students. Asif (2014) study on performance measure of higher education institution pointed out that research performance is also a significant factor and used to evaluate the institution while choosing. Agrey and Lampadan (2014) study further identified Friendly environment, sporting facilities, support system and

learning environment and job prospects too influence the choice an institution.

Thus, many researchers continuously try to identify various emerging considerations of the students while choosing a destination for higher education. Very recently, many higher education institutions make efforts to get international accreditations and placing students on 'Day-1', Number of Placements on Day-1 and salaries offered in foreign currencies and placements in abroad. These efforts tend to create an image and reputation and this reputation identified as a pre-selection variable by Tasirin et al (2015).

Thus, many researchers integrated various marketing and other management concepts to explain student behaviors in the higher education context. This study aims to develop a profile of importance attached to various factors at the time of choosing a higher education destination and an investigation of gender differences in evaluation of these attributes.

It is observed in many different decision situations, male respondents and female respondents' behavior significantly different from each other. To check, whether the parameters considered while choosing a higher education differ significantly across gender, the following hypothesis is framed and tested.

H₁: There is a significant difference between male and female respondents on the importance level of factors considered for choosing a higher education.

3. Research Methodology

Measures

A list of 13 attributes from the various literatures are presented to the students to record their importance while choosing the current higher education institution. The following table summarizes various constructs, source of the scale publication

Table-1 List for factors considered while selecting an institution

S.No	Construct Name	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha [if reported]	Source
1	Soft and hard infrastructure	8	NA	Khanna et al (2014)
2	Alumni and student recommendation	5	NA	Khanna et al (2014)
3	Media influence	4	NA	Khanna et al (2014)
4	Placement opportunities	2	NA	Khanna et al (2014)
5	Fees and location of the higher education institute	2	NA	Khanna et al (2014)
6	Research performance	7	NA	Muhammad Asif Cory Searcy, (2014).
7	Corporate Collaboration	4	NA	Lagrosen, et al (2004).
8	Innovativeness and resonance of the higher education institute	7	NA	Khanna et al (2014)
9	Safe and Friendly Environment	2	0.64	Agrey, and Lampadan (2014).
10	Sporting Facilities	2	0.6	Agrey, and Lampadan (2014).
11	Support System	6	0.8	Agrey, and Lampadan (2014).
12	Learning Environment and Job Prospects	9	0.8	Agrey, and Lampadan (2014).
13	Reputation	3	NA	Tasirin et al. (2015)

Sample and Profile

To test the proposed hypothesis and the model, a sample size of 674 students were selected from engineering colleges in the Tamil Nadu & Pondicherry Union Territory. Fifty one per cent of the samples were male students; 41% of the students were from rural places. Seventy eight per cent of them belong to economically weaker section and studied their higher

secondary education (HSC) in state board and 60% of them scored less than 75% in their HSC.

4. Results & Discussion

All the items are measured on a 7-point scale and an average score for each respondent is calculated.

Table-2 Importance attached while selecting an institution

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	Importance
Safe and Friendly Environment	5.2841	1.59487	Very High
Learning Environment and Job Prospects	5.1344	1.33012	
Reputation	5.0658	1.57906	
Placement	4.9514	1.48267	
Soft & Hard Infrastructure	4.9282	1.07132	
Support System	4.8595	1.34221	Moderate
Fees & Location	4.8232	1.37992	

Research Factor	4.7893	1.38945	Low Importance
Sporting Facilities	4.7396	1.79215	
Innovativeness and resonance	4.6467	1.28865	
Corporate Collaboration	4.6417	1.41124	
Media Sources	4.6243	1.33345	
Recommendation from others	4.5593	1.21171	

The average score corresponding to each factor is used in the analysis. *Safe & friendly atmosphere, Learning Environment and Job Prospects, Reputation, Placement and Soft & Hard Infrastructure* are given very high importance by the students while choosing a particular institution.

Attributes such as *Support system, Fees & Location, Research Factor in the Institution and Sporting facilities* received next level of importance when the students make their choice. Contrary to the general expectations, *Innovativeness, Corporate Collaboration, Media presence and*

Recommendation received very low importance in selecting the institution. Thus, this simple mean calculation provides a base for further analysis of profiling the students based on the factors evaluated while choosing a higher education destination.

Further, to know whether the set of parameters perceived and evaluated differently by the two gender of the respondents [*Hypothesis-H₁*], One-way ANOVA is performed and the results are summarized in the following table.

Table -3 Gender differences on pre-admission factors

Parameters	Category	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-Ratio (Sig.)
Soft & Hard Infrastructure	Male	343	4.7504	1.06442	19.789 (0.000)
	Female	331	5.1125	1.04858	
	Total	674	4.9282	1.07132	
Recommendation from others	Male	343	4.3860	1.15937	14.582 (0.000)
	Female	331	4.7390	1.24005	
	Total	674	4.5593	1.21171	
Media Sources	Male	343	4.4621	1.25831	10.474 (0.001)
	Female	331	4.7923	1.38912	
	Total	674	4.6243	1.33345	
Placement	Male	343	4.7208	1.49410	17.299 (0.000)
	Female	331	5.1903	1.43430	
	Total	674	4.9514	1.48267	
Fees & Location	Male	343	4.6693	1.39988	8.791 (0.003)
	Female	331	4.9827	1.34250	
	Total	674	4.8232	1.37992	
Research Factor	Male	343	4.5727	1.36860	17.393 (0.000)
	Female	331	5.0138	1.37719	
	Total	674	4.7893	1.38945	
Corporate Collaboration	Male	343	4.5926	1.42182	0.846 (0.358)
	Female	331	4.6926	1.40052	
	Total	674	4.6417	1.41124	
Innovativeness and resonance	Male	343	4.4860	1.24373	11.013 (0.001)
	Female	331	4.8131	1.31488	
	Total	674	4.6467	1.28865	
Safe and Friendly Environment	Male	343	5.0292	1.61789	18.310 (0.000)
	Female	331	5.5483	1.52874	
	Total	674	5.2841	1.59487	
Sporting Facilities	Male	343	4.5889	1.83894	4.967 (0.026)
	Female	331	4.8958	1.73131	
	Total	674	4.7396	1.79215	
Support System	Male	343	4.7031	1.27716	9.609 (0.002)
	Female	331	5.0217	1.38988	
	Total	674	4.8595	1.34221	

Parameters	Category	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-Ratio (Sig.)
Learning Environment and Job Prospects	Male	343	4.9602	1.28563	12.179 (0.001)
	Female	331	5.3149	1.35313	
	Total	674	5.1344	1.33012	
Reputation	Male	343	4.9106	1.55986	6.804 (0.009)
	Female	331	5.2266	1.58508	
	Total	674	5.0658	1.57906	

Except the corporate collaboration factor, the male and female respondents evaluate all the other factors differently. Male respondents attached significantly lower importance for all the attributes than the female respondents did. The analysis has brought out one important insight for the administrators in terms of the gender differences and the hypothesis H₁ is accepted for 12 out of 13 factors and except for the corporate collaboration factor.

Gender enrolments in higher education is not so obvious factor; it showed fluctuation in developed country like US, where, 37.1 to 47.4 percent between 1960 and 1976; and growth rates too differed (Karen, 1991). Whereas, country like India, gender equality is not maintained in the higher education system. Thus, the female members, exposure to higher education system is relatively newer factor and the higher evaluations could be the socialization issue of female members in the society.

5. Conclusion

These results strongly suggest that the higher education institution cannot afford to ignore the student's characteristics, particularly, those considerations made at the selection stage. These attributes tend to bias all the offerings made by the

institutions. Processes such as orientation programmes are handy tool to bridge the gap on evaluations. As in the consumer and marketing literatures, behavior of high involvement segment is different from low involvement segment, by recognizing this insight in the higher education institution context; the higher education institutions can be benefited. Understanding this group differences, the administrators may plan to fine-tune the academic related measures better. For instance, more assignments, tutorial sessions may be planned for the group in a disguised manner to create better understanding of higher education system. This will create a better student community in the campus.

From the analyses carried out, it is clear that there are serious challenges for the administrator of an engineering college to create a promotion programme and highlight the salient features of the institutions.

6. Limitation and future research directions

This study has limitations of not considering the factors, such as his CGPA or his Higher Secondary Marks, which may have significant influence while he/she pursuing higher education. By integrating these factors as moderator, further insights may be drawn.

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